

**Cross cultural analysis of food analysis in English, Uzbek and Russian
languages**

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Abstract. This article delves into the information and details about Cross cultural analysis of food analysis in English, Uzbek and Russian languages.

Keywords: languages, Russian, Uzbek linguists, food products, social system, lexical terms, etc.

The development of the society and the change of the social system in the 21st century, along with all the nations, is causing a change in the demands of the consumers of English and Uzbek food products. This puts before us the task of functionally and semantically illuminating the lexical units related to the food products of the two nations. Pragmatic analysis of English and Uzbek food products from the perspective of translation studies, determining their place in the translation of single-component and multi-component terms widely used in consumption from English to Uzbek, or vice versa from Uzbek to English shows similarities and differences.

In fact, keeping pace with the times in every field is a requirement of the present time. In our time, when the process of information exchange is accelerated, it is necessary to clearly understand the meaning of a specific lexical unit during communication in a foreign language, the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek food products and their consumption, and organize communication correctly. In this case, lexical units in order to positively solve the problem of the differences and similarities of the names, types of food products, what part of the day they are consumed, i.e. as breakfast, lunch, dinner or as a snack, seasonal aspects, level of demand, etc. Studying the subtle aspects of functional-semantics of translation serves to expand the scope of practice. The human body receives almost all necessary substances through food and water. The composition of food products and their properties have a direct impact on health, physical development, work ability, emotional state and, in general, the duration and quality of life. It is difficult to find another factor that can affect the human body in such a way. There are many theories about nutrition, and new information appears almost every day, some of which say that meat should be limited, while others say that a diet consisting of only certain products has an effect against all kinds of diseases. They say it can be done. In fact, the human body is a very complex system, for its normal functioning it requires both meat and vegetable dishes. Therefore, it is very important to know the rules of proper nutrition. Following dubious recommendations in this regard can cause serious

health problems. It is considered optimal for a healthy person to eat 4-5 times a day, not exceeding 5 hours between meals. Traditional English breakfast dishes are clearly distinguished by their diversity. Breakfast, that is, the first meal of the day, is of particular importance. A typical English breakfast is thought of as eggs, sausage, toast, mushrooms and baked beans. However, today's English breakfast is unlikely to consist of a payola cereal, a slice of toast, orange juice and a cup of coffee. Many people, especially children, in England love to eat products made from different grains, such as corn, wheat, and oats. And in winter, many people eat porridge or boiled oats. First of all, magmite on toast is a shining example of the originality of English breakfast. It is difficult to imagine a delicious and easy breakfast without toast. While toast doesn't need much explanation, if we talk a little about magmite, a special piece of bread toasted and heated in a toaster, it is made from yeast extract, which gives magmite a distinctly salty taste. There's no denying that magmite has a strong taste, some consumers love magmite on toast, while others can't stand the taste at all. Nature is generous and rich. The hospitable Uzbek table is a clear proof of this.

Delicious fruits and vegetables, melt-in-the-mouth baked goods, warm breads baked in the oven with a unique taste, milk-yogurt products, and so on are proof of the richness of Uzbek food products. Since time immemorial, our mothers have put warm bread and cream on the table early in the morning. As the Uzbek folk

proverbs say, don't leave early and don't leave in the evening, it is advisable to eat nutritious products for breakfast in the morning. Fresh bread with fresh cream, hot tea with honey or sugar, fruits or dried fruits are the basis of breakfast in any Uzbek family. Most importantly, yeast-raised bread bakes in its own heat and steam, creating lots of tiny pores. The porous nature of bread makes it easier for the body to digest it. The chemical composition of bread made from wheat flour mainly contains 30-35% protein, 60-70% carbohydrates, fiber, vitamins B, RR, mineral salts, as well as iron, calcium, phosphorus and other substances. Cream is a thick fat product separated from milk. The first stage of Uzbek processing of milk is to boil it and remove the cream. Warm bread and cream made from cooked milk is a choice that will have a unique taste for breakfast.

Lunch is different according to tradition and according to some people's preferences. Traditional eaters have a light snack for lunch, while others prefer to eat the main meals at dinner time. Despite this, the main meals of the day on Sunday are often eaten at noon, not in the evening. This dish is usually a stir-fry, consisting of roast meat, custard pudding, and two or three types of vegetables. Many students in schools and adults at work keep their nutritious lunches, which contain good calories, in plastic containers. Such a lunch usually consists of a sandwich, a piece of fried meat, fruit and drinks. We can't just call the dishes eaten for lunch "food", because Uzbek cuisine is one of the most colorful dishes in

Central Asia, and lunch dishes should be called "examples of culinary art". Culinary traditions of the settled and nomadic peoples living in the region, accumulated over several centuries, are embodied in the complex of delicious dishes of Uzbek cuisine, which is unique and understandable to all of us today. For example, liquid dishes made from sheep, beef and poultry - soup, and thick dishes - pilaf, which are delicious and unique from each other, are the taste of each region. , the products, the method of preparation, and at the same time the processes of bringing to the table are different. Not only pilaf, but also various somsa, somsa is an integral part of the traditions of Uzbekistan. It is not just a flour product filled with meat or vegetables, it is a tradition passed down from generation to generation. Somsa is loved by everyone and prepared everywhere. There is a wide selection of different somsa on the market: different shapes, different ingredients and prepared in different ways.

As linguoculturemes, phraseological units represent human's national and cultural identity. They are one of the significant means of expressing a nation's lifestyle, its geographical location, as well as the history and traditions of a society united by one culture. In the paper, many lexicographical works have been used to extract English and Uzbek idioms and interpret them from a cultural point of view. The article analyzes English idioms using Uzbek equivalents and it was found that the majority of idiomatic units describe the identity of the nation living in the

ethnic community with a broad cultural aspect. Despite the fact that in both languages phraseological units with food components are formed according to taste, some specific features, appearance, and importance of the dishes, most idioms have very different meanings. A significant place in linguistics is occupied by phraseological units associated with the names of food products, in addition, idioms with food components play an important role in the formation of phraseological units.

The presence of phraseological units with food is essential in order to help people of any nation indicate their attitude to events or express their feelings about situations. Usually, each food product is characterized by some specific features. For instance, while some of them may be sweet, others may be bitter and sour. While analyzing the existing phraseological units in both languages, we can observe that the sweet taste of some idioms serves to represent the goodness or positive qualities of a person, their bitter or sour taste helps to reflect people's difficulties and negative traits. However, depending on the culture of the country, the national world picture, the food products that represent these characteristics may be different in both languages.

There are many approaches to understanding the concept. By the concept, we mean the operational content unit of memory, mental lexicon, conceptual system and language of the brain, the whole picture of the world, reflected in the human

psyche. This definition of the concept that more accurately reflects its concept. It should be noted that in the concept, from the point of view of culture, the value, figurative and conceptual sides are highlighted. The study of these components contributes to the understanding of a specific concept by carriers of a particular linguistic culture. It is the presence of common, universal concepts that ensures communication between peoples. At the same time, each culture forms its own stereotypes of consciousness and behavior, based on its own vision of the world. The proverbs and sayings clearly express the norms of behavior of this or that society, this or that social group. Considering the proverbial fund of languages of different peoples, we trace the "image" of the picture of the world and the image of the world through the prism of the proverbs of these peoples, thus revealing the features of material and spiritual culture, the connection of proverbs with the history of the people. In addition, a comparative analysis of these proverbial funds allows you to get an idea of the cultural and proverbial mentality characteristic of each culture separately.

Many proverbs in Russian and Uzbek have the same essence, which, however, can be conveyed in completely different words due to the fact that the proverb is based on different associations. However, not all existing proverbs have exact or close matches in other languages, since the history of the development of each nation is individual. Proverbs and sayings reflect centuries-old folk wisdom

and, as a rule, are easy to remember. If we consider food in terms of reflecting the topic of wealth / poverty, then Russian linguoculture is characterized by associations of wealth with dairy products: как сыр в масле кататься; молочные реки, кисельные берега [like cheese in butter to roll]; milk rivers, jelly banks - with the names of sweets: одна рука в меду, другая – в патоке [one hand is in honey], the other is in molasses. A characteristic sign of wealth and prosperity for Russian linguoculture is the image of bread and salt: живем – хлеб жуем, а ино и посаливаем; хлеб да соль [we live-we chew bread, and in other ways we salt it; bread and salt] (a wish at a meeting). At the same time, bread without salt can be a sign of poverty. A bright image symbolizing poverty is the image of bread and water: сидеть на хлебе и воде [sitting on bread and water]. Similar, partly opposite meanings, actualized by proverbs containing the word bread, are due to the wide scope of the concept, which is traditionally covered by this word in Russia).

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